

This is the existence happens absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If nothing happens, therefore something happens, however, if something happens, therefore nothing happens. And so the outcome of that paradox is something happens. However, if something happens, therefore nothing happens, however, if nothing happens, therefore something happens. And so the outcome of that paradox is that nothing happens. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that either something happens or nothing happens.

This is the existence is happening absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If nothing is happening, therefore something is happening, however, if something is happening, therefore nothing is happening. And so the outcome of that paradox is that something is happening. However, if something is happening, therefore nothing is happening, however, if nothing is happening, therefore something is happening. And so the outcome of that paradox is that nothing is happening. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that either something is happening or nothing is happening.

This is the existence has happened absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If nothing has happened, therefore something has happened, however, if something has happened, therefore nothing has happened. And so the outcome of that paradox is that something has happened. However, if something has happened, therefore nothing has happened, however, if nothing has happened, therefore something has happened. And so the outcome of that paradox is that nothing has happened. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that either something has happened or nothing has happened.

This is the existence whimmed in absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If nothing is whimmed in, therefore something is whimmed in, however, if something is whimmed in, therefore nothing is whimmed in. And so the outcome of that paradox is that something is whimmed in. However, if something is whimmed in, therefore nothing is whimmed in, however, if nothing is whimmed in, therefore something is whimmed in. And so the outcome of that paradox is that nothing is whimmed in. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that either something is whimmed in or nothing is whimmed in.

This is the existence explains itself twin paradox, which is made of the following components: The existence happens absolute paradox paired with the existence is happening absolute paradox, the extra of the existence has happened absolute paradox, and the outcome of the existence whimmed in absolute paradox, where this twin paradox goes as followed: If paired existence happens absolute paradox with the existence is happening absolute paradox, then existence has happened absolute paradox, however, if existence has happened absolute paradox, then existence whimmed in absolute paradox, however, if existence whimmed in absolute paradox, then paired existence happens absolute paradox with the existence is happening absolute paradox.

This is the hobby absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is a toy, it is therefore a model, however, if it is a model, it is therefore a toy. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is a model. However, if it is a model, it is therefore a toy, however, if it is a toy, it is therefore a model. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is a toy. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either a model or a toy.

This is the ask a question and receive an answer absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is a clock, it is therefore a ruler, however, if it is a ruler, it is therefore a clock. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is a ruler. However, if it is a ruler, it is therefore a clock, however, if it is a clock, it is therefore a ruler. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is a clock. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either a ruler or a clock.

This is the exactly absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is the same, it is therefore different, however, if it is different, it is therefore the same. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is different. However, if it is different, it is therefore the same, however, if it is the same, it is therefore different. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the same. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either different or the same.

This is the what it is absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is literal, it is therefore figurative, however, if it is figurative, it is therefore literal. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is figurative. However, if it is figurative, it is therefore literal, however, if it is literal, it is therefore figurative. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is literal. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either figurative or literal.

This is the it works twin paradox, which is made of the following components: The ask a question and recieve an answer absolute paradox paired with the hobby absolute paradox, the extra of the what it is absolute paradox, and the outcome of the exactly absolute paradox, where this twin paradox goes as followed: If paired ask a question and recieve an answer absolute paradox with the hobby absolute paradox, then what it is absolute paradox, however, if what it is absolute paradox, then exactly absolute paradox, however, if exactly absolute paradox, then paired ask a question and recieve an answer absolute paradox with the hobby absolute paradox.

This is the maker absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is the existence explains itself twin paradox, therefore it is the it works twin paradox, however, if it is the it works twin paradox, therefore it is the existence explains itself twin paradox. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the it works twin paradox. However, if it is the it works twin paradox, therefore it is the existence explains itself twin paradox, however, if it is the existence explains itself twin paradox, therefore it is the it works twin paradox. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the existence explains itself twin

paradox. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the it works twin paradox or the existence explains itself twin paradox.

This is the day time absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is fluttery, it is therefore swift, however, if it is swift, it is therefore fluttery. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is swift. However, if it is swift, it is therefore fluttery, however, if it is fluttery, it is therefore swift. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is fluttery. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either swift or fluttery.

This is the month timespace absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is the cause, it is therefore the effect, however, if it is the effect, it is therefore the cause. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the effect. However, if it is the effect, it is therefore the cause, however, if it is the cause, it is therefore the effect. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the cause. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the effect or the cause.

This is the year space absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is motionless, it is therefore in motion, however, if it is in motion, it is therefore motionless. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is in motion. However, if it is in motion, it is therefore motionless, however, if it is motionless, it is therefore in motion. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is motionless. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either in motion or is motionless.

This is the decade image absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is fixed, it is therefore flexible, however, if it is flexible, it is therefore fixed. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is flexible. However, if it is flexible, it is therefore fixed, however, if it is fixed, it is therefore flexible. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is fixed. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either flexible or fixed.

This is the date mirror absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is the fraction, it is therefore the root, however, if it is the root, it is therefore the fraction. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the root. However, if it is the root, it is therefore the fraction, however, if it is the fraction, it is therefore the root. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the fraction. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the root or the fraction.

This is the eternal hallucination twin paradox, and it is made of the following components: The paired trinity of the day time absolute paradox and the month timespace absolute paradox and the year space absolute paradox, the extra of the decade image absolute paradox, and the outcome of the date mirror absolute paradox, where this twin paradox goes as followed: If paired trinity of the day time absolute paradox and the month timespace absolute paradox and the year space absolute paradox, then decade image absolute paradox, however, if decade image absolute paradox, then date mirror absolute paradox, however, if date mirror absolute paradox,

then paired trinity of the day time absolute paradox and the month timespace absolute paradox and the year space absolute paradox.

This is the fantasy absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is the maker absolute paradox, therefore it is the eternal hallucination twin paradox, however, if it is the eternal hallucination twin paradox, therefore it is the maker absolute paradox. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the eternal hallucination twin paradox. However, if it is the eternal hallucination twin paradox, therefore it is the maker absolute paradox, however, if it is the maker absolute paradox, therefore it is the eternal hallucination twin paradox. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is the maker absolute paradox. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either the eternal hallucination twin paradox or the maker absolute paradox.

The eternal hallucination of the eternity that currently exists, is the eternal hallucination of LSD, and I made it that way.

This set is timed as 15:58, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.